

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT PLAN

MATILDE DELIVERABLE 2.8

Version 1.1

MATILDE has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement No 870831

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

- H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth
- H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 2.8 – Stakeholder involvement plan

Authors: Marika Gruber, Christina Lobnig, Sara Scheiflinger, Kathrin Stainer-Hämmerle

Contributors: Jan Amcoff, Elena Apollonio, Simone Baglioni, Lisa Bauchinger, Stefanie Bogomilova, Mariza Bona, Francesca Calo, Signe Lise Dahl, Thomas Dax, Elena Di Bella, Olga Davydova-Minguet, Ulf Hansson, Lauri Havukainen, Trude Hella Eide, Christopher Hofbeck, Anna Klerby, Anna Krasteva, Jussi Laine, Raúl Lardiés Bosque, Per Olav Lund, Ingrid Machold, Tina Mathisen, Pirjo Pöllänen, Micheline van Riemsdijk, Giulia Rossi, Maria Røhnebak, Evelina Staikova, Susanne Stenbacka, Tobias Weidinger, Fatma Yilmaz-Elmas

Approved by Work Package Manager of WP 2: Stefan Kordel (FAU) on 31.8.2020

Approved by Project Coordinator: Andrea Membretti (EURAC) on 31.8.2020

Picture credits: Cover: CUAS (Women ready to start), Lavonne Bosmann (Holiday, Cover); Paolo Libertini (Bourcet); p. 10: Christopher Thomson (Matilde Website 4); p. 17: Lavonne Bosmann (Roman Chickens); p. 40: CUAS (Women ready to start2); p. 68: Lavonne Bosmann (Holiday)

Proofreading: Marvin D. Hoffland

Carinthia University of Applied Sciences: Villach, August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4005933

MATILDE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870831

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 870831 for the European Commission. It does not necessary reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

CONTENT

List of figures.....	5
List of tables.....	6
List of acronyms.....	7
Executive summary.....	8
1 Stakeholder involvement in MATILDE project.....	11
2 Introduction to MATILDE.....	12
2.1 Aims and goals.....	12
2.2 Fundamental definitions and project concepts.....	13
2.2.1 Third country nationals.....	13
2.2.2 Rural and mountainous areas.....	14
2.3 Methodological approaches.....	15
2.3.1 Qualitative and quantitative research.....	15
2.3.2 Participatory research.....	16
3 Theory of expert and stakeholder involvement.....	18
3.1 Transdisciplinary research approach in detail.....	18
3.2 Participatory research in detail.....	20
3.3 Stakeholder involvement as civic engagement and empowerment process.....	22
3.4 Stakeholder Involvement from the perspective of the Citizen Science concept.....	25
3.5 Helix models of innovation.....	28
3.6 Roles and tasks of stakeholders.....	32
3.7 Stages of participation.....	33
3.8 Ethics of public participation.....	36

3.9	Conclusion and MATILDE approach.....	38
4	MATILDE stakeholders.....	41
4.1	Project structure.....	41
4.2	Research and local partners by country.....	42
4.3	Further project stakeholders.....	49
5	Process of identifying and engaging stakeholders in MATILDE.....	50
5.1	Who? Identification of stakeholders.....	50
5.1.1	Mind Mapping.....	52
5.1.2	The 6-3-5-Method.....	53
5.1.3	Environment Analysis.....	53
5.1.4	ABC-Method.....	53
5.2	Where? Thematic assignment of stakeholder to areas of action.....	54
5.3	When? Stakeholder involvement schedule.....	58
5.4	How? Methods of stakeholder and expert involvement.....	59
5.5	Afterwards? Living document and stakeholder documentation.....	66
6	Stakeholder involvement as planned per partner, WP and task.....	69
6.1	Stakeholders on European and global level.....	69
6.2	Matrix network map.....	72
6.3	Agreed schedule of stakeholder involvement.....	74
	Bibliography.....	82
	Annex.....	90
	Annex 1: Template stakeholder landscape Matrix.....	90
	Annex 2: Template stakeholder Involvement Schedule.....	92

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Conceptualization of the ‘Quadruple Helix’	29
Figure 2: Further visualization of the Quadruple Helix model	30
Figure 3: Visualization of the adapted Quadruple Helix model for MATILDE	32
Figure 4: Stages of involvement within the MATILDE project	34
Figure 5: IAP2’s Code of Ethics for Public Participation Professionals.....	36
Figure 6: MATILDE partner structure.....	41
Figure 7: Steps of MATILDE stakeholder involvement and engagement.....	51
Figure 8: Exemplary representation of a mind map.....	52
Figure 9: Mid-level theory by Ager and Strang.....	55
Figure 10: Visualization of the MATILDE areas of action based on the mid-level theory of Ager & Strang.....	56
Figure 11: Exemplary network map based on the stakeholder landscape matrices	73

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Stages of involvement within the MATILDE project, explanations.....	35
Table 2: MATILDE research and local partners.....	42
Table 3: Further stakeholder categories.....	49
Table 4: Extract from the template of the stakeholder landscape matrix.....	55
Table 5: Extract from the template of the stakeholder involvement schedule.....	58
Table 6: Extract from the draft template of the stakeholder documentation.....	67
Table 7: Listings of stakeholders on European level.....	69
Table 8: Listing of stakeholders on international/global level.....	71
Table 9: Stakeholder network map, labelling system.....	73
Table 10: Stakeholder involvement per WP and task as agreed on by the WP leaders.....	74
Table 11: Detailed stakeholder involvement listing.....	75

LIST OF ACRONYMS

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
LP	Lead Partner
LoP	Local Partner
PA	Participatory Research
RP	Research Partner
SIP	Stakeholder Involvement Plan
TCN	Third Country National
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The involvement and promotion of active engagement of stakeholders within a project that is driven by an approach based on transdisciplinary and Participatory Action Research (PAR) and aims at exploring the impact of migration within a multi-national context is of utmost importance. The broad range of actors and stakeholders involved in the MATILDE project includes practitioners with varying backgrounds, researchers from different disciplines and NGOs, political decision-makers, public administrations and even private businesses on different territorial levels, and therefore implies the need for coordination.

This stakeholder involvement plan is divided into two parts: the first is the plan as described in the project proposal and the second is a "living document", which will be extended throughout the project duration.

The goal of the first part of the stakeholder involvement plan (Deliverable 2.8) is to guarantee the active and timely participation of stakeholders at different levels (e.g., EU, national, regional, provincial and local). It should serve as a guidance and support the project partners in order to better navigate the overall process of engaging interest groups and to describe both theoretical and practical foundations, thus, creating a common understanding for all actors involved. This part of planning details the types of stakeholders, the anticipated level of participation and affiliation of involvements to work packages in order to establish a temporal connection to ensure that stakeholders are addressed with an adequate method and through appropriate channels.

The second part, the "living document", forms the basis of a continuous exchange between the MATILDE partners in regards to their work with stakeholders and was designed to better correspond to the reality of project work, which is inherently subject to constant change. It should offer the opportunity to reflect on the specific project needs and respective work processes, to elaborate on lessons learned and to jointly discuss acquired knowledge. It is considered as a chance to gain insights on how cooperation within EU projects as well as stakeholder involvement takes place, which

participation methods are suitable for respective stakeholder groups and future projects. This part of the stakeholder plan will be a possibility to discover the potentials of stakeholder engagement and to benefit from the experiences and differing points of views from the partners with various backgrounds from different countries, all working towards the same goal. In this way, networks such as think tanks with various kinds of stakeholders can be created that will last beyond the duration of the project and can make a sustainable contribution to initiating positive changes.

INTRODUCTION

1 STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT IN MATILDE PROJECT

In recent times, citizen participation processes, e.g. on issues such as the design of personal living environments, have gained particular importance. One approach of disability studies in this context is “Nothing without us about us” (Hermes, 2006). This shows that it is extremely important to involve the people affected in the design of measures so that they are developed in a need-centered way on the one hand and are accepted by the people who will continue to work or live with them on the other. However, there is another perspective to consider here: the interaction of different actors, in this sense stakeholders, to develop innovations and improved measures. Science plays an important role in this process and has long claimed absolute competence and the necessary knowledge for itself. As will be shown in the course of the SIP, various concepts of citizen participation have increasingly broken up this mindset.

MATILDE project is designed to take a multi-perspective view on different phenomena and to involve a variety of stakeholders. MATILDE follows a multi-level governance approach, which recognizes the involvement and interdependence of different actors and their interaction at different levels of government to achieve specific thematic objectives (Gruber 2020; for more details on the multi-level migration governance approach of MATILDE, see Kordel & Membretti, 2020a, MATILDE Deliverable 2.4).

However, it makes a difference whether citizens or stakeholders are involved in the practical design of their living environment or in a research project. These differences arise mainly from the fact that the capacity to act in research projects is usually limited. For example, after empirical findings have been collected, concrete (political) recommendations for action can be worked on, but the project often ends with the implementation of the developed measures. These limitations are considered in the present SIP, its schedules and proposal for participation degrees.

The present stakeholder involvement plan (SIP) is specifically aimed at the MATILDE research partners, but can also be used as a basis for stakeholder involvement in other research projects. The SIP should

serve research partners as a guide for stakeholder engagement in the different work packages as well as tasks.

Based on the approach of agile project management, stakeholder involvement is seen as a dynamic process that must adhere to high ethical principles and see stakeholder involvement as a continuous process. The principles that the SIP of MATILDE follows are presented in the following chapters.

2 INTRODUCTION TO MATILDE

This section gives an overview of the MATILDE project itself, its goals and the most important terms.

2.1 AIMS AND GOALS

The Horizon2020 research project MATILDE aims to examine migration impacts on local development and territorial cohesion in European rural and mountain regions, to improve the integration of Third Country Nationals (TCNs) and local development. As MATILDE aims to improve knowledge on the social and economic impacts of migration processes, the project conducts quantitative and qualitative analysis of the effects of TCNs arrival and settlement on the social and economic domains. Behind this aim stands the desire to promote socially inclusive and territorially balanced growth, which could be stimulated by improved urban-rural/mountain connections and reflecting the potential of TCNs stocks and flows for local development (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831).

In detail, MATILDE objectives are to (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831):

- develop a conceptual and methodological framework for the multi-scale and multidimension assessment of migration impact,
- assess the multi-dimension of social and economic impact of migration,
- assess migration impact through action-research in rural and mountain regions,

- improve migration governance and territorial cohesion,
- develop new narratives on migration impact.

2.2 FUNDAMENTAL DEFINITIONS AND PROJECT CONCEPTS

As the MATILDE aims and objectives make clear, MATILDE focus is on two fundamental concepts: TCNs and rural/mountain areas. Since both of these concepts are decisive for the research and are also relevant for the stakeholder involvement, an overview of both concepts is given below (for more details see: Kordel & Membretti, 2020a, MATILDE Deliverable 2.4).

2.2.1 THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS

Based on Art. 3(1) Directive 2008/115/EC (Return Directive) and Art. 2(6) of Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code), the European Commission (2020) defines a TCN as: “Any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code).” Following this definition, nationals of Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered as TCNs. Referring to this definition, TCNs legally residing in the European Union (EU) are the target group of EU integration policies (see the latest Action Plan on the integration of TCNs, COM (2016) 377 final).

As noted in the MATILDE Deliverable 2.4 - Report on conceptional frameworks on migration processes and local development in rural areas, MATILDE focus is on economic migrants, family migrants and forced migrants (including asylum seekers, refugees and status holders). Specific subgroups (e.g. unaccompanied minors, victims of trafficking in human beings, single parents) will be considered in some local case studies (Kordel & Membretti, 2020a).

2.2.2 RURAL AND MOUNTAINOUS AREAS

In the MATILDE project, a description and categorization of MATILDE regions have been completed based on the EUROSTAT's Urban-Rural typology (see Kordel & Membretti, 2020b, MATILDE Deliverable 2.1). This typology focuses on population density and has led to a classification into two groups of MATILDE regions: “more rural” and “less rural”. The classification “more rural” includes regions classified in the EUROSTAT's Urban-Rural typology as “predominantly rural”. Regions defined by the EUROSTAT typology, referred to above, as “intermediate” and “predominantly urban” are classified as “less rural”. To better examine the specificities of rural and mountain areas, more aspects than population density and distribution have to be considered. Such aspects, taken into account in Deliverable 2.2 - Database on spatial features and TCNs distribution, are, e.g., land use, accessibility of services or access to resources like education or employment. To provide comprehensive regional profiles, further territorial indicators will be considered in the analyses of the social, economic and territorial impacts of TCNs in MATILDE regions (Bona, 2020; for more information see Kordel & Membretti, 2020a, MATILDE Deliverable 2.4).

2.3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

The following chapter gives a short overview of the scientific approaches pursued within the MATILDE project and the reasons why they were chosen.

2.3.1 QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH

The attempt to break down empirical social research and divide it into different approaches immediately results in the well-known division into quantitative and qualitative social research. Qualitative social research tends to use an epistemological approach as a basis for investigations in order to depict realities that are individually meaningful. Quantitative social research uses thereby a more hypothetical-deductive approach common in natural sciences in order to explain objects of investigation and create prognoses and theories of cause-and-effect correlations (Töpfer, 2007). The objective also commonly is to test newly proposed hypotheses based on findings obtained through qualitative procedures and furthermore to be able to either verify or falsify them, sometimes resulting in recommendations for the future (Töpfer, 2012). A simple attempt to highlight the fundamental difference between these two traditions is to refer to the number of cases or observations. While qualitative methods are typically used to investigate (a) single case(s) (case study approach) or a smaller number of cases, quantitative methods usually involve a much larger sample in order to be able to arrive at more general or generalisable conclusions (Stockemer, 2019).

In the MATILDE project a mixed-methods approach is applied, using quantitative and qualitative methods. The social impact as well as the economic impact of TCNs will be assessed in a qualitative manner with the help of in-depth and narrative interviews as well as focus groups, and in a quantitative manner by descriptive and interpretative statistics (univariate and multivariate analysis) (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831).

2.3.2 PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH

In addition to the quantitative and qualitative methods, MATILDE adopts an action-research approach that emphasises the agency of migrants and the site-specific features of the regions involved. Via 13 case studies in the MATILDE regions, the urban-rural connections and flows of people, economic resources as well as cultural exchange are analysed. With an action-research approach the two-level consortium, research partners and local partners working in the field of TCNs' integration, will work together to co-construct the migration impact assessment in rural and mountain areas by engaging a variety of further stakeholders, such as local policy makers, migrants' organizations, public authorities in charge of service provision, non-profit organizations and associations. The action-research should stimulate the transdisciplinary creation of knowledge about the social, economic and spatial impacts of TCNs at the local level in rural and mountain regions.

For each case study an own approach based on the thematic developed, the actors involved and the specific territorial features, is applied. For all case studies, interviews and focus groups with stakeholders and local experts will build the basis. Depending on the focus of the case study, further techniques and tools are considered as open space technology (OST), world café or participatory videos (MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831).

The applied mixed-methods and transdisciplinary-participatory MATILDE research approaches build the foundation of stakeholder involvement. The explanations on the MATILDE research approaches make clear that the broad range of stakeholders play a major role in the project and could have different roles: They can be consulted and place informants in interviews and focus groups, but could also be co-designers of improved policies or simply multipliers and disseminators of project results.

The nature of transdisciplinary and participatory research is discussed in Chapter 2 in more detail.

THEORY OF EXPERT & STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

3 THEORY OF EXPERT AND STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

This chapter intends to give an overview of the extensive theoretical discourse on the topic of stakeholder and expert involvement, and then to present concrete methods that can be used for this purpose.

3.1 TRANSDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH APPROACH IN DETAIL

Understanding research as a comprehensive process means that both qualitative and quantitative aspects are present and interact continuously (Atteslander, 2010). Kelle attempts to overcome this dualism of methods, for example, by putting forward the thesis that the weaknesses of one approach can be compensated by the strengths of the other and vice versa (Kelle, 2007).

Transdisciplinary research approaches therefore aim at combining different elements from the realms of qualitative as well as quantitative research performed by actors with backgrounds in various disciplines in order to better adjust to the needs presented while pursuing the exploration of a scientific question or problem (Hadorn et al., 2008).

In other words, it describes the research efforts of investigators from different disciplines, who work together to create new conceptual, theoretical, methodological, and translational innovations by integrating and moving beyond discipline-specific approaches (Harvard Transdisciplinary Research in Energetics and Cancer Center, 2012).

While often used synonymously, there are noteworthy differences between the terms of transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary research. Through interdisciplinarity it is possible to convey topics of different disciplines. This is based on the assumption that a problem in a single discipline cannot be fully understood and that knowledge can only be increased by including other subjects. A research result would then no longer be the sum of its technical parts, but the product of successful cooperation (Brauer et al., 2018). The main difference between the two terms is that transdisciplinary

projects include non-academic participants, while interdisciplinary projects do not (Tress et al., 2005).

There are problems that cannot solely be solved with traditional methods of academic disciplines. Some problems require problem-oriented, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches (Brewer, 1999). The proclaimed goals of transdisciplinary research are to grasp the complexity of a posed problem, take a wide range of scientific and practical perceptions into consideration, connect practical and specific knowledge with abstract and promote what is perceived as common good through the development of knowledge and practices (Hadorn et al., 2008).

Even though the use of transdisciplinary research approaches is implied in some cases and considered suitable, there are several issues that can occur as different disciplinary methods and new research methods need to be successfully integrated to enable effective and efficient learning processes and the used methods have to be understood thoroughly (Scholz & Tietje, 2002).

The implementation of transdisciplinary research can be characterized with three components (Brandt et al., 2013):

The process phases:

- collaborative identification und structuring of a problem,
- analysis of the problems,
- integration and application of the results.

The types of knowledge produced during the project: The produced knowledge (which is shared between scholars and participants) can be divided into three groups (ProClim, 1997):

- system knowledge: is gained through the observation of the system,
- target knowledge: is all knowledge about the desired target state,
- transformation knowledge: is needed to foster the transformation process.

The intensity of the involvement of practitioners in the project:

- The connection between practitioners and scientists is an important element of transdisciplinary approaches. The involvement of the practitioners within the projects can occur at different intensities. It ranges from the one-way communication of information, two-way communication (consulting) to collaboration and empowerment (practitioners get the authority to decide) (Brandt et al., 2013).

The transdisciplinary research approach chosen by MATILDE is based on the action research approach developed by Lewin. Its main focus is on empowering and helping minority groups to gain self-confidence and self-determination by helping them to seek “independence, equality and cooperation” (Lewin, 1946). Action research proceeds on the premise that there are no generalizable solutions when engaging stakeholders, but that because contexts can vary significantly they instead have to be adapted to the unique respective circumstances and needs. Participation is an essential pillar of this approach since “action research works on the assumption that all people who affect or are affected by the issue investigated should be included in the process of inquiry” (Stringer, 2014, p. 6).

In order to achieve the project goals aimed by MATILDE and, in addition, to initiate change processes and create the basis for future networks that will last beyond the project lifetime, stakeholders should be continuously involved and asked to actively participate in the project.

3.2 PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH IN DETAIL

Participatory research is a general term describing research approaches that influence and explore social reality through cooperation. The aim is to understand and change social reality. Two objectives define participatory research. This is firstly the participation of social actors as co-researchers and secondly measures for individual and collective self-empowerment and the aim of empowering those partners. The concept of participation is of central importance. It refers both to the participation of social actors in research and to their participation in society. A fundamental concern of participatory

research is to enable more social participation through participation in research, which is seen as a value-based endeavor. Social justice, human rights, environmental justice, and other value orientations are driving forces and participatory research mainly focuses on the people who participate in it. Their perspectives, their individual and collective (self-)empowerment and their learning processes are therefore seen as crucial. Participatory research is thus never a purely academic undertaking, but always a joint project with non-scientific, social actors (von Unger, 2013).

This results in participants to be seen as valuable co-researchers by participatory action research (PAR). Since they have detailed knowledge about the circumstances of their own life and social environment, it would not be beneficial to reduce their part-taking to being passively consulted. Preferably, they should have an active part in the whole process by examining, engaging, interpreting and reflecting on their social world and forming their sense of identity (Hearne & Murphy, 2019).

In order to clarify the thematic differentiation of participatory action research from other approaches, it is worth mentioning at this point what it is not (McTaggart, 2010):

- PAR differs from the usual work of practitioners (regardless if they are academics or workers) as it is more systematic and collaborative in the collection of evidence and in the planning of change.
- PAR is more than just problem solving, because it includes problem posing. Problems are not seen as plain pathologies. It is an important part of understanding and improving the world and to understand the effects of certain changes on it.
- PAR is not something that is imposed on subjects of research. People are not treated as objects but as autonomous, responsible and knowing agents, who work together to achieve change and improvement.
- PAR is not a technique, method or an implementation of a policy. Truths created outside of the involved community or truths created by researchers who work in the community but treat PAR as an object are not accepted. It does however, see propositions from outside as test-worthy.

- PAR aims at achieving more than testing hypotheses or coming to conclusions. PAR focuses not only on the interpretation of situations but on their change. This form of research is systematically evolving and changing the researcher as well as the situation.

3.3 STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT AS CIVIC ENGAGEMENT AND EMPOWERMENT PROCESS

Defining civic engagement turns out to be no trivial matter, since there is no universal definition, as it is very much influenced by the interests and points of view of those who try to define it (Adler & Goggin, 2005). Nevertheless, we may look at the definition attempt of Delli Carpini. He described civic engagement as individual and collective actions with the overall objective to identify and address issues of public concern. Civic engagement is not limited to one fixed format but it is very versatile: It can be practiced as individual voluntarism, organizational involvement or electoral participation. Well known examples are working in a soup kitchen, writing a letter to an elected official or serving on a neighborhood association. An important part of civic engagement is its efforts to directly address problems, to work jointly with other community members to solve problems or communicate with institutions of representative democracy (Delli Carpini, 2009).

As it encompasses so many different facets, it can also be discovered through different theoretical positions (Edwards, 2004):

- From an *analytical point of view*, civil society can be seen as a part of society distinct from states and markets: It was formed to advance common interests and to facilitate collective action. Civil society or the 'third sector' in this sense includes all associations and networks between the family and the state, but no firms.
- From a *normative point of view* civil society cannot be seen as a realm of self-interest but a realm of service. It helps to form attitudes and values like trust, cooperation, tolerance and non-violence.

- Civil society can also be seen as a public sphere for an *exercise of 'active citizenship'* in pursuit of a common interest, public deliberation and rational dialogue. It plays an important role in democracy and development.

During the past decades, the academic interest in political participation grew in the established democracies. This interest was caused by a concern about declining levels of civic engagement (e.g., low electoral turnout) (Ekman & Amnå, 2012).

There are several points that underline the importance of civic engagement. It may contribute to the building of capacities and independence, while also increasing tolerance and responsibility. Furthermore, communities and democracy directly benefit as voluntary involvement causes the production of public goods and joint activities to be easier (Skocpol & Fiorina, 1999). Engaging in civic activities is also beneficial to a functioning society, because cooperative actions give citizens the opportunity to pursue common goals. Moreover, it is indicated that the level of public involvement in civic activities affects the health of a society (Scheufele & Shah, 2000).

The main element that drives civic engagement activities, however, is trust, a core element of social capital. **Social trust** plays an important role for individuals to work together for a common good (Jennings & Stoker, 2004) and together with civic engagement, they share a symbiotic relationship. An involvement in volunteer work and civic associations benefits individuals by improving political skills, trust and confidence in others. This helps addressing social and political needs (Jennings & Stoker, 2004).

However, it is noted that also economic inequality has an influence on civic engagement and civic spirit (the trust in other people). People who do not trust others or who belong to less fortunate socio-economic groups are less likely to participate in civic life. Inequality depresses participation either directly or indirectly through its effects on trust. Where inequality is higher, people with less resources compared to others may feel powerless and will perceive that the political system does not represent

their views. As a result, they are more likely to opt out of civil engagement. Trust rests on a foundation of economic equality. An unequal distribution of resources will lead to distrust between people from different backgrounds as they do not see each other as facing a shared fate. Trust is also linked to optimism and the possibility to attain control over one's environment. In conclusion, it can be said that inequality leads to lower levels of trust and has an indirect effect on civic participation, which has to be kept in mind when planning stakeholder involvement measures as to **not exclude marginalized or vulnerable groups** (Uslaner & Brown, 2005).

As with all areas, civil engagement is subject to constant change and innovation, which in turn enables new forms of participation that may be more accessible to a broader public. Digital services for example, open up new possibilities for supporting civic engagement as well as new fields of activity. Digital means can support civic engagement or be the content of the engagement itself and can be separated into four groups (Hinz et al., 2014):

- information about the civic engagement or the organization (e.g. website, newsletter),
- networking between committed people and organizations (e.g. social networks, blogs chats),
- mediation of resources and assistance and the actual cooperation (e.g. communication and fundraising platforms etc.),
- digital collaboration through content creation and improvement, communication, teaching and consulting, development of technical solutions, participation of citizens, crowdfunding.

Participatory democracy is promoted through civic engagement mechanisms and the internet can be used as a tool to do so. Social media platforms like Facebook have an important role in practicing civic engagement as well, as they cannot only be used for social networking but community mobilization, social protest and political activities. Moreover, wide range, quick response time and interactive creation possibilities make it very suitable for political discourses (Taiwo & Opeibi, 2016).

3.4 STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE CITIZEN SCIENCE CONCEPT

Public participation in science is a well-known and widely used concept. Prior to the late nineteenth century nearly all scientific research in North America and Europe was conducted by amateurs (Vetter, 2011). They were pursuing research because of an interest in specific topics or questions, as part of religious or government activities or as part of subsistence (Porter, 1978). Many amateurs were recognized experts in their field and conducted research of the same or even better quality as done by professional scientists of that time (Vetter, 2011). Such as Johann Peter Süßmilch, who was originally a pastor, and is considered as the “father of German statistics and demography” due to his accurate population statistics (Ebert, 2001). In addition, neither Isaac Newton nor Gregor Mendel were academic representatives of their subjects. It has to be noted that modern science owes its emergence in particular to civic involvement (Finke, 2014).

The terms civic or public science are sometimes used synonymously with citizen science. Terms like do-it-yourself science (DIY-science), transdisciplinary and public history research have many similarities with citizen science (Pettibone et al., 2016).

Over the past 150 years a professionalization of science took place and the role of amateurs as peers or colleagues to professional scientist was diminished (Lepczyk et al., 2020). Over time, the techniques involved in developing and managing citizen science projects have improved both the scientific and educational outcomes. This is due to the advances in communications, transportation and computing (Lepczyk et al., 2020). Rick Bonney further adds the areas of data management, online resources and communication technology and studies of the quality and value of citizen science data (Bonney et al., 2009). Its activities range from data collection for established research projects and the financing of research projects to crowdfunding and internet-based mega-projects such as the Wikipedia-project (Finke, 2014).

Citizens don't need a "PhD" in astrophysics to classify stars, a degree in biology to study birds, or a degree in computer science to program intelligent sensors to study the behavior of bees. Today science is open to anyone who is curious and wants to create knowledge. Citizens can already become researchers in many disciplines, so called citizen scientists, (BMBF, 2020), in order, e.g., to explore and analyze their own living environment or work together on political recommendations for specific fields of action which concern them. Citizen science is used to actively involve the public in projects to generate new knowledge and raise awareness of certain topics. Nevertheless, these projects have genuine science outcomes. Professional scientists as well as citizen scientists benefit from taking part as it creates opportunities for learning, harbors social benefits and in the best case provides personal enjoyment. Another aspect is the satisfaction gained through one's contribution to solutions aimed at improving local, national or international issues and taking part in creating suitable policies (Hecker et al., 2018).

Peter Finke sees citizen science as one of the strongest expressions of civic engagement in civil society. It contributes to broad access to knowledge, involves active participation by the society in the acquisition of knowledge and strengthens the position of laypersons vis-à-vis experts. Thus, citizen science plays an outstanding role in the development of the democratic knowledge society (Finke, 2014). Citizen scientists can be involved in several phases of the scientific process and they should receive feedback from the project. The project data and metadata will be made available to the public, and, if possible, the results should be published in an open-access format. The citizen science programs are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, societal or policy impact and the participant experience. It should be noted, that citizen science has, like any other research approach, limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled (Hecker et al., 2018).

The objectives, participants and methods of citizen science projects vary greatly. Nevertheless, it is possible to establish general **criteria for success** (Beck, 2012):

- At the beginning of the project there should be a question, which can be realistically answered.
- The methods for collecting the data must be simple, standardized and understandable.
- The quality of the collected data must be assured.

- The project should also be coupled with knowledge transfer.
- The participants and the public should be informed about the results.
- An appealing website and apps make citizen science projects more attractive.
- Areas and tasks have to be, following (Dransch et al., 2018), formulated for which citizen participation provides added value.
- Citizens must be persuaded to participate in the formulated projects in sufficient numbers.
- The scientific topics and tasks must be understandable, comprehensible and interesting.
- Procedures must be developed that enable public participation in such a way that scientifically usable results can be achieved.

There are many advantages to citizen science, some of which are presented below as examples (Pettibone et al., 2016):

Citizen science benefits science by:

- giving inspiration for new research topics (through new ideas, methods, questions and societal knowledge),
- creating large datasets that are adaptable to different usage.
- creating an increase in public acceptance of research results.

Citizen science benefits society by:

- creating an opportunity for co-creation of transparent research,
- creating the opportunity for societal transformation (e.g., towards sustainability),
- a democratization of the discursive meaning of science,
- strengthening civil society and government agencies.

Citizen science benefits participants by:

- developing opportunities for contributions to scientific discoveries,
- improving the understanding of science and advancement of scientific qualifications,

- facilitating participation in political decision-making through scientific contributions,
- creating opportunities for critical examination of scientific results,
- being fun and promoting sharing.

3.5 HELIX MODELS OF INNOVATION

Models that are strongly linked to the concept of citizen science are the **helix models**, which are used to map the interaction of different actors in the field of (social) innovation.

Helix innovation models are based on the idea that through an interactive process involving different spheres of actors, innovation can be generated as output. The models assign and formalize a role to the sphere of actors. The main actors of these innovation-generating processes are industry, universities, governments, civil societies and natural environments of society. The protagonist of the spheres can contribute to innovation through sharing and teaching of their knowledge. The role of knowledge as well as the number and scope of spheres have been increased over time, because society becomes more and more interactive. Therefore, different helix models with different amounts of spheres exist (Cavallini et al., 2016).

- The **triple helix** model, developed by Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff (2000), contains three helices that intertwine and generate a national innovation system (Carayannis & Campbell 2009). The innovation model is based on the relationships between academia/university, industry and state/government and emphasizes how crucial higher education is for innovation. However, citizens and end-users are seen as passive recipients, who use the services and products developed. This lack of participation may lead to products and services that are not used, a lack of transparency, a lack of understanding of end-users, frustration and technical but not social innovations (Leifson, 2018). In literature it is agreed that the extension of the triple helix model by a further helix would be important, but it was not clear which should be the fourth helix (Hasche et al., 2019).

- The **quadruple helix** model, extended and conceptualized for the first time by Carayannis & Campbell (2009), contains the actors of the triple helix but adds another helix, which they originally defined as “media-based and culture-based public”. This should include aspects like “creative industries”, “culture”, “values”, “art” or “life styles”. For them, the “proper ‘innovation culture’ is key for promoting an advanced knowledge-based economy” (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009).

Figure 1: Conceptualization of the ‘Quadruple Helix’

However, other scientists have also argued for including the artistic, cultural and values perspectives in innovation processes. Some scientists argue for the involvement of both, a civil society approach and an end-user approach, which in the end has come down to define the

fourth helix as “civil society” (for a presentation of the discourse on the development of the fourth helix and the opinions expressed in the literature, see Hasche et al., 2019). The helix “civil society” should demonstrate that society should be seen as driver for knowledge production and innovation (Cavallini et al., 2016). The involvement of citizens in innovation development leads to user-oriented innovations, better acceptance by the end-users, a higher level of trust towards innovators and innovations, empowerment of citizens and providing them an active role in the innovation system (Värmland County Administrative Board, 2019). The actors of this helix model are representatives from all members of society, public authorities, industry, academia, and citizens (Cavallini et al., 2016).

- Public authorities are the government, regional development agencies, policy makers and (in some countries) formal health care providers.
- Industry describes businesses (e.g. private health care providers) and business clusters.
- Academia consists of research and development bodies as well as universities.
- The fourth actor of the quadruple helix are citizens (Leifson, 2018).

Quadruple Helix Model

Figure 2: Further visualization of the Quadruple Helix model

Since the quadruple helix is a model for innovation and collaboration which focuses the citizen or end-user perspective, the model is used in innovation processes where the focus on the

needs of citizens is central (e.g. health care, public e-services) (Värmland County Administrative Board, 2019).

In this way, more successful, user-oriented innovations can be created, which end-users are more likely to accept and therefore use. Further advantages can be seen in the creation of social benefits at a lower overall cost while simultaneously increasing citizens' empowerment, as the general public may experience more trust towards the innovators and is more willing to be an active part of the innovation system (Leifson, 2018).

For a more successful collaboration, the specific stakeholders should be defined through **stakeholder mapping**. Moreover, it is important to make sure that all stakeholders are involved, motivated and are open minded (Leifson, 2018).

The quadruple helix model can be used in several phases of an innovation process, as various properties of innovation activity determine if the helix model is suitable for a certain phase (e.g. the goals, the context, the owner or initiator of the innovation process) (MacGregor & Carleton, 2012).

- Lastly, the **quintuple helix** model adds yet another helix and therefore another perspective, namely that of natural environments of society and economy, which contribute to developing knowledge production and innovation (Carayannis et al., 2012).

Since the tripe helix model is missing a part of crucial importance for MATILDE and the quintuple helix model is mainly used in the context of environmental issues, climate change and overall environment studies, the focus for MATILDE lies on the quadruple helix model and its implications for further proceeding in engaging stakeholders.

- Associations and clubs
- Asylum and refugee care
- Education and training institutions
- EU-Level umbrella organizations
- International umbrella organizations
- Internal stakeholders
- Local partner
- NGOs
- Non-organized/other interest groups
- Political decision makers
- Private businesses
- Public administrations
- Public welfare service providers
- Research facilities and individual researchers
- Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups

MATILDE Quadruple Helix Model

Figure 3: Visualization of the adapted Quadruple Helix model for MATILDE

3.6 ROLES AND TASKS OF STAKEHOLDERS

Today's society is differentiated, based on division of labor and can be subdivided into several social subsystems in which again different functions are performed. This means that there is no uniform "space of experience" which is common to all, but rather many different sections of reality, which means that there is special or expert knowledge that is only available to the respective group creating and experiencing it (Sprondel, 1979).

Involving experts and stakeholders usually serves one of the following purposes (Wassermann, 2015):

- **Provision of knowledge:** The aim is to gather the specific knowledge of the individuals or groups involved. The result of such a process can be both a summary of the collected knowledge and the creation of new knowledge.
- **Forecasting and estimation:** In this context, the focus lies on providing accurate statements for the future based on the knowledge gathered.

- **Evaluation, prioritization and transfer of knowledge or innovations:** The aim here is to have findings evaluated by experts and stakeholders in order to arrive at recommendations. If the goal is not the evaluation itself, it is also common practice to develop a systematic collection of jointly developed evaluation criteria for various options of action and decision-making.
- **Exchange, consultation and dialogue:** This includes, for example, communication with interest groups or citizens, as well as consulting services in research. Experts can be involved, for example, in citizens' conferences or similar participation formats, in order to inform interest groups. Their knowledge can also be directly used as input and not as a service of moderating exchange between other stakeholders. Exchange of knowledge and experiences of different involved parties and the possibility for dialogue are of essential importance when trying to facilitate participatory approach.
- **Implementation and multiplication:** Although sometimes not explicitly addressed, the aim is often that the results of research efforts are approved and supported by the groups involved, and that they are carried into their communities and local environment, especially in the case of developed methods for change and/or recommendations for action.

It should be noted that a clear separation between these purposes is often not completely possible, as in practice, overlaps do exist (Wassermann, 2015).

3.7 STAGES OF PARTICIPATION

There are many ways of involving individuals and groups in processes, but not all of them can be considered participatory. Participation in social sciences is considered to be more than mere attendance but rather a partaking in activities in the sense of participating but also making use of shared resources (Chabal, 2009). For this reason, and because each activity has different objectives that need to be achieved, there are different degrees of participation, which are mapped in various stage models across disciplines. Based on "Arnstein's ladder of citizen participation" (Arnstein, 1969) and the further developed participation pyramid (Straßburger & Rieger, 2019) a separate stage model

was derived for MATILDE with regards to the different possible degrees of involvement within the project, which can be achieved.

Figure 4: Stages of involvement within the MATILDE project

In the following, the individual stages are briefly described and exemplary methods that can be used for each involvement stage are provided in order to gain a better understanding of the differences.

Table 1: Stages of involvement within the MATILDE project, explanations

Stage	Name	Description
1	Information	At this stage, stakeholders are only informed with the aim of disseminating first results. It is not intended to gain knowledge by requesting their expertise or points of view.
2	Consultation within a given framework	This stage represents the next step in which participants are consulted by means of predefined or standardized forms of inquiry.
3	Open consultation	Similar to the previous stage, the aim is to involve stakeholders through consultation, but is not restricted by the constraints of a predetermined framework.
4	Interactive involvement	The level of mere questioning is exceeded by moving on to a joint and interactive approach.
5	Networking	This stage represents the transition from guided and accompanied activities to independent networking among the stakeholders involved and with other groups, ideally to establish lasting and sustainable connections beneficial to defined project goals.
6	Joint creation	The highest level of participation within the project process can be understood as the joint development of recommendations that are feasible and oriented towards the needs of the stakeholders. The aim is to activate the stakeholders and enable them to implement these recommendations and initiate sustainable transformation processes.

At this point it must be mentioned that there is still a continuum of participation strength even within the individual participation levels. For example, the open consultation (level 3) can consist of obtaining oral feedback at a low-threshold level, i.e., on policy recommendations or known good practices in one's own field of action, or of conducting in-depth biographical interviews.

3.8 ETHICS OF PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Participation is a complex process that often not only reveals critical perspectives, but also offers many opportunities. However, taking advantage of these opportunities relies on the cooperation of all parties involved.

Figure 5: IAP2's Code of Ethics for Public Participation Professionals

In addition to the previous subjects, another important aspect to be considered for all activities involving the work with stakeholders is that of ethics. By taking on the role of the initiator of exchange, researchers are ultimately required to take responsibility for a professional and ethical approach.

Following the example of other H2020-projects (Panopoulou et al, 2019), IAP2's Code of Ethics for Public Participation Professionals will be discussed in this section to provide a basic framework for respectful and effective interactions with stakeholders (International Association for Public Participation, 2017).

The individual points are seen as building blocks that build on each other in order to maintain the interests and integrity of those who participate.

The individual blocks are described as follows (International Association for Public Participation, 2017):

1. **Purpose:** Supporting public participation as a process to make better decisions that incorporate the interests and concerns of all affected stakeholders and meet the needs of the decision-making body.
2. **Role of practitioner:** Enhancing the public's participation in the decision-making process and assist decision-makers in being responsive to the public's concerns and suggestions.
3. **Trust:** Undertaking and encouraging actions that build trust and credibility for the process among all the participants.
4. **Defining the public's role:** Carefully considering and accurately portraying the public's role in the decision-making process.
5. **Openness:** Encouraging the disclosure of all information relevant to the public's understanding and evaluation of a decision.
6. **Access to the process:** Ensuring that stakeholders have fair and equal access to the public participation process and the opportunity to influence decisions.
7. **Respect for communities:** Avoiding strategies that risk polarizing community interests or that appear to "divide and conquer."
8. **Advocacy:** Advocating for the public participation process and not advocating for interest, party, or project outcome.
9. **Comments:** Ensuring that all commitments made to the public, including those by the decision-maker, are made in good faith.
10. **Support of the practice:** Monitoring new practitioners in the field and educate decision-makers and the public about the value and use of public participation.

The extent to which an approach based on a strong ethical framework can contribute to a positive course of implementation is shown by a summary of the most prevalent challenges in stakeholder involvement (Niederberger, 2015).

- **The choice of the appropriate method:** In stakeholder involvement, methods are often used that are not known to the participants. If these are openly discussed and collaboratively applied, participants show a fundamentally higher level of acceptance than if they feel like test subjects. Communication and trust are key elements in successful execution.
- **Expert dilemma:** As a general rule, it can be assumed that the participants have their own motivations, backgrounds and values, therefore creating a dialogue can be challenging. A neutral, qualified and trustworthy moderation, which approaches everyone openly and provides an atmosphere of not being judged, is therefore essential.
- **Acceptance of the results:** Communicating results in a timely manner, sharing them with the participants and giving them the opportunity to comment on them or make corrections is essential to ensure positive acceptance. It is important not to bypass stakeholders, but to maintain their integrity and appreciate the input they have provided and the time they have invested.

3.9 CONCLUSION AND MATILDE APPROACH

The aforementioned explanations show that transdisciplinary-participatory research with an active involvement of a wide range of stakeholders plays a major role in the MATILDE project. Stakeholder participation in the various work packages and stages of the project was already considered in the project planning. Stakeholder involvement in the MATILDE project takes in consideration the different theoretical stakeholder involvement approaches. In its methodological implementation, the project is basically oriented towards transdisciplinary and participatory research. As it attempts to achieve new insights in social and economic impacts of TCNs (integration) on local and rural development and aims to provide new tools (i.a., methodological toolbox for social and economic impact assessment, self-assessment toolbox for policy makers) an approach is required which leads to innovative solutions. Therefore, the helix models are consulted which make clear that innovations need the equal cooperation of academia and research, political and public authorities, businesses and civil society. In

fact, the MATILDE stakeholder groups can be grouped into these four categories, knowing that there can be overlaps among stakeholder groups and that a stakeholder (e.g., a training institute) can be both, public or private businesses. Stakeholder involvement needs always the know-how on civic engagement and empowerment as the different stakeholder groups need to be “awakened”, interested in the project, motivated to participate and keep their participation going over the project period, in order to finally work together on viable policy recommendations, which are at best also implemented and applied by the stakeholders themselves in their areas of action and organizations. At the highest level, stakeholders are empowered to apply the tools and project results developed in their own environment and can thus continuously explore their fields of action, which means adopting a citizen science attitude and contributing to on-going improvements.

MATILDE STAKEHOLDERS

4 MATILDE STAKEHOLDERS

In this chapter the project stakeholders of MATILDE are described in further detail. First, the general partner structure is presented, followed by a list of the partners per country in order to then address those stakeholders that still need to be engaged in the course of the project.

4.1 PROJECT STRUCTURE

The incorporation of stakeholders' knowledge is achieved on the one hand through the cooperation of research partners and local partners within MATILDE two-level consortium to ensure a multi-actor perspective to the project. On the other hand, the project benefits from the involvement of a broad range of further stakeholders.

Figure 6: MATILDE partner structure

The local partners represent a territorial hub within the 13 regions that identify and coordinate together with the research partners and the relevant (local) stakeholders for the project in order to promote the joint preparation of the migration impact assessment and maintain an inclusive approach. They are also of utmost importance for disseminating the project results and thus contributing to sustainable change processes. Both research and local partners have the opportunity to consult the advisory board, which consists of experts from various disciplines and provides expertise and methodological support for the process.

4.2 RESEARCH AND LOCAL PARTNERS BY COUNTRY

The research and local MATILDE partners span across Europe and represent a broad variety of academia and practical experience in the fields of TCN integration and local/rural development. Both types of partners work together in order to activate a wide variety of stakeholders in their home countries and regions, but also on European and international levels. The following overview of all research and local partners (LP = lead partner, RP = research partner, LoP = local partner) illustrates their heterogeneity and specific knowledge and shows that their respective expertise enables them to get access to the different stakeholder groups.

Table 2: MATILDE research and local partners

Country	Participant	Description (of Partner)	Role
IT	<p>Accademia Europea Di Bolzano</p>	<p><i>EURAC</i> is an applied research centre and through an interdisciplinary approach, it works on the protection of minorities and multilingualism, investigate climate change, draw up sustainable development plans based on renewable energy, and contribute to the health of the community by conducting biomedical studies.</p>	LP

DE		Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen Nürnberg	<i>FAU</i> is one of the largest research universities in Germany with five faculties covering the entire spectrum of modern academic disciplines. Cultural values, religions and human rights in general and migration in specific represent an outstanding research focus of <i>FAU</i>	RP
SE		Uppsala Universitet	<i>UU</i> was established in the year 1477. The Department of Social and Economic Geography gains and disseminates knowledge in human geography and geography. Migration issues are central in departmental research, and, for example, in projects focusing on immigration and belonging, trans localism, segregation and racism.	RP
AT		Fachhochschule Kärnten - gemeinnützige Privatstiftung	<i>CUAS</i> offers about 30 bachelor and master programs in four fields of study: civil engineering & architecture, engineering & IT, health sciences & social work, and management. <i>CUAS</i> is in the first third of the Austrian's strongest applied universities in research with 17 thematic research groups and three research centers and has carried out more than 140 national & European research projects with more than 200 partners.	RP
IT		University of Parma	<i>UNIPR</i> is a state university and, as such, is self-governing and has research, administrative, organizational, and accountancy autonomy. The university with its about 28,000 students is organized in nine departments distributed across three campuses. <i>UNIPR</i> is in the 30 top performing entities in Italy in the major EU funding schemes FP7 and H2020 awarding more than 90 grants so far.	RP
AT		Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft und Bergbauernfragen	The <i>BAB</i> is a research unit affiliated to the Austrian Ministry of Sustainability and Tourism targeted at analysis of agricultural economic issues, rural and mountain development research. A specific thematic task are studies on social aspects of local development to foster local	RP

		initiatives and on migration processes in rural areas, as well as concentrating on opportunities of immigration to regional development.	
FI	Ita-Suomen Yliopisto	<i>UEF</i> is one of the largest universities in Finland and is involved in an internationally leading interdisciplinary social science and regional research. The Karelian Institute of <i>UEF</i> is a multi-disciplinary and international recognized research unit focusing on regional development, cultural studies, borders and migration.	RP
BG	New Bulgarian University	<i>NBU</i> is based on the liberal idea of education, relating the acquisition of knowledge and professional qualification. <i>NBU</i> is a student-oriented, autonomous academic institution for the cultivation of enterprising persons, who are responsible for their own development in a democratic environment, civil society, market relations, and European and world integration.	RP
TR	Istanbul Bilgi Universitesi	<i>BILGI</i> is a private university and a non-profit institution which has several research centers specialized in youth studies, children studies, civil society studies, migration studies, sociology, education studies and human rights studies. Istanbul Bilgi University is a renowned institution with several different social outreach projects ranging from combating poverty to teaching European integration.	RP
NO	Hogskolen I Innlandet	The academic offerings of <i>INN</i> cover a vast number of subject areas ranging from ecology and agricultural sciences to social sciences. The research is centered on the five following main issues: welfare services and local communities; economy, both within industries and in society at large; tourism, leisure and cultural industries; work and integration; management of natural resources, including planning.	RP

<p>SE</p> <p>Hogskolan Dalarna</p>	<p><i>HAD's</i> main fields of research involve researchers from different disciplines, and from other institutes of higher education. The DUCID research center at <i>HAD</i> conducts research in the field of intercultural studies and offers commissioned education opportunities to external organizations, while also holding debate evenings and conferences that have a wide focus on issues such as cultural pluralism and cultural diversity.</p>	<p>RP</p>
<p>ES</p> <p>University of Zaragoza</p>	<p><i>UNIZAR</i> is a public higher education and research institution and is ranked 8th in Spanish universit in terms of scientific and academic production, according to the Academic Ranking of World Universities. <i>UNIZAR</i> has been participating in European Projects since the FP4. The institution has participated in several projects, as coordinator and partner.</p>	<p>RP</p>
<p>TR</p> <p>Hayata Destek Derneği</p>	<p><i>STL</i> is a humanitarian aid agency founded with the principal objective of working with municipalities to help them meet their basic needs and rights. <i>STL</i> is involved in humanitarian assistance, protection of displaced populations, and the resilience of disaster-affected communities concentrating on the needs of children, youth, women, and the most vulnerable.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>BG</p> <p>Caritas Bulgaria</p>	<p><i>CARITASBG</i> is a non-profit organization implementing social work to support vulnerable people in society. The main areas on which it concentrates its activities are: providing social, health and educational services; responding to emergency situations; promoting advocacy activities before the Bulgarian government to develop and implement long-term and effective social policies that lead to sustainable improvement of the quality of life of the poor and vulnerable people.</p>	<p>LoP</p>

<p>AT</p> <p>okay.zusammen leben / Verein Aktion Mitarbeit</p>	<p><i>OKAY</i> is a competence center on migration and integration. Its main activities include to run an information and advice center; to develop, guide and support concrete integration measures for migrants; to implement programs (focus: language skills of children and youth) and to involve the province in an international exchange of experiences and knowledge.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>SE</p> <p>Landstinget Dalarna</p>	<p><i>DALARNA</i> is responsible for publicly financed healthcare, medical care and regional development. It is the main regional political organization and is in many ways independent from the national government. One of the departments handles the question of integration of migrants at a strategic regional level, working directly with the municipalities, the national government, authorities and the civil society for an improved integration process and a sustainable economic and demographic growth.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>AT</p> <p>Stadt Villach</p>	<p><i>VILL</i> is located close to the borders with Italy and Slovenia and it is the seventh largest city in Austria. The Office for Integration promotes the integration of immigrants and the coexistence of immigrants and locals in Villach. To fulfil this task, the Office for Integration works with public, non-profit and private institutions and with immigrant organizations.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>FI</p> <p>Siirtolaisuusinstituutti</p>	<p><i>MIF</i> has four main tasks: promoting the collection, storage and documentation of research material relating to international and internal migration; carrying out and promoting migration research; publishing research reports, books and articles on migration; developing co-operation between universities and special organizations related to migration and providing information services about migration.</p>	<p>LoP</p>

<p>FI</p> <p>Joensuun seudun monikulttuurisuus yhdistys ry</p>	<p><i>JOMONI</i> is a non-profit civil society organization and its goal is to promote multiculturalism and to prevent the discrimination and exclusion of immigrants. The association is open to all and the activities are mainly carried out by volunteers. Its three main areas are: supporting multi-channel inclusion to increase well-being, promoting women's rights, status and participation and supporting and inspiring civic activities.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>IT</p> <p>Città metropolitana di Torino</p>	<p><i>CMTORINO</i> is a wide second level local authority and its territory is the largest European metropolitan area. It's one of the most important Italian industrial areas and it has been involved in 85 European projects regarding issues like migration, environment, tourism, education, international cooperation search and innovation, transportation and sustainable mobility, education and training.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>IT</p> <p>Caritas Diözese Bozen-Brixen</p>	<p><i>CARITASBZ</i> is a religious foundation with the task of promoting the testimony of love for neighbors in the Christian community and solidarity between people in society. It offers services ranging from the fulfilment of primary needs up to integration paths with language courses, job search, accompanies migrants and creating a network of integration and making migrants part of the local community.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>UK</p> <p>Convention of Scottish Local Authorities</p>	<p><i>COSLA</i> is the representative voice of local government in Scotland, provides political leadership on national issues, and works with all of Scotland's Local Authorities to improve local services and strengthen local democracy. The Migration, Population and Diversity (MPD) team within COSLA works specifically on key issues relating to migration in Scotland.</p>	<p>LoP</p>

<p>DE</p> <p>Tür an Tür - Integrationsprojekte gGmbH</p>	<p><i>TAT</i> is a registered association and has considerable experience of European Union programmes including transnational projects which have developed methods and instruments for the integration of migrants. It focuses on migration, employment, skills audits and policy and practice development at local, regional and national levels.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>NO</p> <p>Innlandet County Council</p>	<p><i>OPP</i> is a political organization at the regional level in Norway. The County's main goal is regional development, and has important societal responsibilities within education, transport, planning, climate and the environment, business development and international cooperation, culture and cultural heritage, and public health, in addition to resettlement of refugees and integration of immigrants.</p>	<p>LoP</p>
<p>ES</p> <p>Province of Aragon</p>	<p><i>ARAGON's</i> objective is to ensure the protection of citizens in situations of social emergency and the commitment to an active social inclusion strategy. It is about putting the social services system at the center of the political agenda and the person as the center of the system.</p>	<p>LoP</p>

4.3 FURTHER PROJECT STAKEHOLDERS

In order to assist the research partners in the identification of stakeholders for the MATILDE project, to simplify the mapping as well as to prevent overlooking interest groups of importance, stakeholder categories have been developed following an epistemologically exploratory approach.

In the course of several joint brainstorming sessions by the SIP developing team, consulting existing stakeholder plans and in consideration of the stakeholder categories used by the EU Commission in its “public consultation on the integration and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background” (launched in July 2020) to develop a new version of the action plan on integration and inclusion (European Commission, 2020) and by means of several tests using the example of Austria and correction loops, the following stakeholder categories were formed. They are intended to give a comprehensive and detailed picture of the stakeholder landscape regardless of the country-specific context in which they are applied.

Table 3: Further stakeholder categories

Stakeholder category	Examples
Associations and clubs	Migrant communities, sports clubs, women’s associations
Asylum and refugee care	Basic care, accommodation, refugee social work
Education and training institutions	Schools, private tutoring services, kindergarten, language schools, adult education centers
Internal stakeholders	Advisory board, ethic committee, project officers, national funding contact points, MATILDE supporters
International umbrella organizations	Migration Policy Institute (MPI), International Organization for Migration (IOM), Alliance in the Alps
EU-Level umbrella organizations	Red Cross EU Office
Local partner	MATILDE local partners
NGOs	Regional offices of Red Cross, Caritas, Diaconia and smaller (local) non-governmental organizations (e.g., providing

	integration support services)
Non-organized/other interest groups	Private volunteers, individual migrants and their family and friends (not-organized in ethnic communities)
Political decision makers	Mayors, heads of ministries, district governors, provincial governors, municipal/city councils
Private businesses	Privately owned businesses
Public administrations	Municipalities, district administrations, provincial government office, regional managements, federal ministries of ... (e.g. health...), public libraries
Public welfare service providers	Employment market service, statutory health insurance, legal pension insurance
Research facilities and individual researchers	Academia and other research facilities
Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	Chamber of labour, chamber of commerce, trade union confederation, student unions

5 PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING AND ENGAGING STAKEHOLDERS IN MATILDE

The following section will present the process of identifying and engaging further, external stakeholders within the MATILDE project as well as methods and tools that were used to guide this undertaking and the next steps to ensure a continuous involvement during the project duration.

5.1 WHO? IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

In principle, the process of stakeholder identification within the MATILDE project can be divided into three steps, the third and last one representing the living document. For each of these steps, the appropriate tools for MATILDE have been developed in the form of tables and templates to ensure a consistent and holistic approach.

Figure 7: Steps of MATILDE stakeholder involvement and engagement

The Stakeholder Landscape Matrix (Step 1) serves as a general collection and overview of stakeholders relevant to the project. Therefore, the research partners were asked to freely discuss which stakeholders from their defined project area (e.g., case study region) or country should be involved, which contacts could be used and from whose experience and input a benefit could be generated, regardless of the individual project phases or thematic areas in which the exchange takes place.

The identification of further stakeholders could be done by an optional action to start the process: a

brainstorming session on relevant MATILDE stakeholders in each project region could take place. In order to conduct and visualize this brainstorming, different **creativity techniques** apart from a classical mind-map could be used and thus help to stimulate this process. Some selected methods are presented below (see chapter 5.1.1 to 5.1.4).

5.1.1 MIND MAPPING

In a mind map, a specific question or topic is viewed and visualized by placing the main topic in the middle of the visualization medium (online tools, flipcharts etc.) and then trying to add results and idea of a brainstorming session in subtopics. Mind maps can already be a first construct in the process of structuring early ideas, they can be used as a tool for mere brainstorming, which does not follow any order or they may visualize highly structured content.

Figure 8: Exemplary representation of a mind map

5.1.2 THE 6-3-5-METHOD

In a first step, 6 people gather together to brainstorm on a topic. In the case of the stakeholder involvement plan, each of the participants takes a large piece of paper and writes the first three stakeholders to be involved in the project in the first column of a matrix. After a specified time (e.g., 1-3 minutes) the sheet is passed on and the ideas of the predecessor are supplemented by new ones or the existing ideas are further elaborated in the second column. The sheet is passed on until everyone has had a chance to work on each paper once. In this way, different stakeholders, existing contacts and the expected benefits can be worked out creatively to get a first overview of interest groups that should be involved by the respective partner. 6 participants, 3 ideas each, 5 times passing on. The number of participants can be flexibly adjusted according to staffing conditions, but a minimum of three to four people is recommended (Arbeiter, 2016).

5.1.3 ENVIRONMENT ANALYSIS

With the help of the environment analysis, stakeholders, influences and frame conditions can be assessed. For the visual creation of this analysis different software and online tools can be used as well as boards or flipcharts. For the visualization the project is placed in the center and possible stakeholders are gathered surrounding it. The strength of the influence and possible links between the stakeholders can be shown with the help of lines and the line width connecting them to the project (König & Volmer, 2008).

5.1.4 ABC-METHOD

The ABC method is another creative process in which a multitude of potential stakeholders can be identified. The people participating in the brainstorming each write the letters of the alphabet vertically on a large piece of paper. Within the context of a set time limit, an attempt is made to identify names of stakeholders for as many letters as possible. Optionally, this can also be done in the form of several rounds, where after only a short time the sheet is passed on (Arbeiter, 2016).

5.2 WHERE? THEMATIC ASSIGNMENT OF STAKEHOLDER TO AREAS OF ACTION

In a next step the research partners were asked to assign all relevant stakeholders (gathered in the brainstorming; see chapter 5.1) to different areas of action and further project relevant areas.

The mid-level theory of Ager and Strang (2008) is strongly integrated in the conception and implementation of MATILDE and is therefore also considered in the process of stakeholder engagement in order to involve stakeholders from all relevant fields and enable them to participate.

Ager and Strang's (2008) mid-level theory presents a model for analyzing integration from two perspectives: the view of migrants (in their theory of refugees) and the view of the local respective receiving society. In their theory, ten interdependent dimensions (see figure 9) build a hierarchically pyramid, with the dimension "rights and citizenship" on its peak. This dimension serves as the basis and is the key of access to employment, housing, education and health sector. These four dimensions are defined by Ager and Strang (2008) as "markers & means" of integration. In their theory, they identified three dimensions (social bridges, social bonds and social links) which builds "social connection" and plays an important role for the integration processes at local level. The two dimensions "language and cultural knowledge" as well as "safety and stability" serve as "facilitators" to employment, housing, education and health (Ager and Strang 2008; for further details on the theory adopted to the MATILDE conceptual framework, see Kordel & Membretti, 2020a, MATILDE Deliverable 2.4). As "spatial mobility" plays an important role for inclusion/exclusion especially in peripheral rural and mountain areas and can therefore be seen as a further facilitator, the model was expanded (Weidinger et al., 2017; Weidinger, 2018).

Figure 9: Mid-level theory by Ager and Strang

Source: Ager & Strang, 2008, p. 170; adapted by Weidinger et al., 2017, p. 50.

For the work on the MATILDE stakeholder involvement plan, the hierarchical order of the dimensions is dispersed as for stakeholder involvement all dimensions are of equal importance. In the sense of collecting stakeholders, however, the fields in the matrix were arranged as equivalent.

Table 4: Extract from the template of the stakeholder landscape matrix

Stakeholder category	Economy & Employment	Housing	Health	Education	Language & Culture
Associations and clubs					
Asylum and refugee care					
Education and training institutions					
Internal stakeholders					
International stakeholders					

Furthermore, to reflect the actual range of integration related dimensions and areas of action covered by MATILDE, they are revised in the case of stakeholder identification. The dimensions "social bridges", "social bonds" and "social links" have been grouped together under the collective term "social connection", since a separation in the sense of stakeholder engagement does little to improve the results. Furthermore, the areas of action are enlarged by the dimensions "mobility" (as proposed by the adopted model) and "rural/regional development" (one key focus of MATILDE project). The "dissemination & networking" area is also added as one aim of Horizon projects is to create impact at various target audiences (i.a., policy makers at different territorial levels, academia, local stakeholders or journalists).

Figure 10: Visualization of the MATILDE areas of action based on the mid-level theory of Ager & Strang

The allocations to the various areas of actions are only intended to help partners to obtain a complete and structured overview. The result is a “living map”, which is not binding, but could and should be constantly updated and supplemented and thus kept “alive”.

The research partners were asked to allocate each stakeholder to the fields in which they fit best; “correctness” is in that sense neither achievable (as some stakeholders can fit in more than one category) nor the main focus. For example, an assignment to the area of “safety & stability” would be appropriate if the focus of a stakeholder is to be on the secure living situation of TCNs. An assignment to the area of “economy & employment” would include measures directed at access to labor market, economic growth and entrepreneurship. Measures aiming at topics such as social cohesion, polarization and integration would fit the area of “social connection”. The area “rural/regional development” would be used if the primary focus of an institutional or individual stakeholder is on research or measures for the development of rural areas. Lastly, the area of “dissemination & networking” was introduced if, for example, a certain stakeholder or stakeholder group is not thematically engaged, but still informed about the project, acts as a multiplier, or contributes to the dissemination. By assigning institutions, groups and individuals (collected via the brainstorming phase) to the areas of action and predefined stakeholder categories, the partners are given a first overview of who (which stakeholders) is in principle to be involved.

If helpful, a further distinction can be made between the “national” (N), “regional” (R) and “local” (L) levels in order to identify easily the relevant stakeholder groups according to their territorial and administrative/political belonging. The visualization of the level of belonging helps to make gaps in the supply and missing contact points visible at certain levels. The stakeholders identified in the Stakeholder Landscape Matrix can also help to build up (a) thematic think tank(s) on regional, national or European levels. As was shown during the completion of the matrix, this is an extensible model, in which, depending on the (national/regional) framework of some partners, additional areas of action that focus on aspects perceived as particularly relevant can be added.

5.3 WHEN? STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT SCHEDULE

In this second step, the stakeholders gathered so far are put into a temporal context by assigning the planned engagement per category to work packages and tasks. When filling out the template the partners have the possibility to indicate a planned involvement and the planned stage of participation (see chapter 3.7, stages of participation) by selecting the numbers (1–6).

Table 5: Extract from the template of the stakeholder involvement schedule

	WP1								WP2							
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6		
Associations and clubs																
Asylum and refugee care																
Education and training institutions																
Internal stakeholders																
International umbrella organizations																
EU-Level umbrella organizations																
Local partner																
NGOs																

The feedback from partners is collected and compared. The work package leaders are then asked to formulate minimum requirements regarding their levels of participation, and thus the activities and plans to be set, for the tasks they are responsible for. These minimum requirements for stakeholder involvement in the specific work packages and tasks should serve as guidance for the partners and point of comparison to the partners' individual planned stakeholder involvement.

5.4 HOW? METHODS OF STAKEHOLDER AND EXPERT INVOLVEMENT

To involve experts and stakeholders after successfully identifying them, there are many different methods, the choice of which varies according to purpose and context. In the following, some of the most common methods are listed as examples to give an overview of possible approaches sorted by the adapted stage model of participation (Rosenbrock & Hartung, 2012). These methods are based on a literature research that was conducted with a focus on both scientific literature as well as experiences of other projects on the topic of stakeholder engagement and the following section presents a summary of these results (Wassermann, 2015; van der Gaast, 2015; Panopoulou et al., 2019; Government of Western Australia, 2015).

For each level, methods

are listed together with possible tools

that could be useful.

Stage 1: Information

The first stage is still one of the preliminary stages of participation and involves informing individuals, groups or organizations without attempting to capture the knowledge or experience of the stakeholders. Dissemination activities in particular often take place at this stage.

M
E
T
H
O
D

Information sharing

 Fact sheets/newsletters

 Websites/Blogs

 Information sessions

 Correspondence/Informal personal exchange

Stage 2: Consultation within a given framework

In contrast to the first stage, this is the first, which not only promotes one-way communication, but also establishes contact with stakeholders to gather knowledge. However, this is done within a predetermined framework by means of obtaining information that is more uniform or already based on a certain structure.

Quantitative, highly structured surveys

As the name suggests, the aim of quantitative surveys is to obtain quantitative results, i.e., results based on numbers, in order to be able to make statements. Therefore, a larger sample size is usually important in order to be able to draw statistically relevant and thus meaningful conclusions. The advantage of highly pre-structured, quantitative surveys lies in the fact that certain topics can be researched in a targeted manner and a large number of respondents can be reached with comparatively less time and expense, e.g., when using an online survey tool. A variation of this survey is the opinion poll in which the opinion of the target group is specifically asked by the investigators, while the respondents are usually aware of the fact that they are contributing their own opinion. This can be used to actively participate in decisions or influence their outcome.

- 🔧 Interviews with standardized questionnaires
- 🔧 Online surveys with predetermined answering options
- 🔧 Telephone survey with predetermined answering options

Stage 3: Open consultation

In contrast to the previous stage, the last step of the preliminary stages of participatory processes also focuses on the questioning of the target group: however, this is performed by using methods created in an open manner as to not restrict the respondents in their choice or elaboration answer to a great extent.

Qualitative surveys and interviews

In the literature, this term is used to summarize those surveys which do not aim to obtain many results on predetermined questions, but to shed light on detailed experiences, life worlds, life courses and views of a comparatively smaller number of subjects.

- 🔧 Online surveys based on open questioning
- 🔧 Guideline-based interviews

The purpose of the guide is to lead through the interview and not to lose focus. It is important to keep the questions open and to encourage a conversation between the interviewer and the respondent. Just as standardized questionnaires are best checked for their suitability by means of literature-led design and pre-testing, the same is advised when developing guidelines for interviews. According to Kaiser, the "intersubjective traceability", which is to be applied in the process of the survey, data collection and analysis, can hardly be maintained to the same extent in the course of qualitative surveys as is the case with quantitative investigations. Irrespective of this, researchers should provide complete documentation in regards to the process, the framework conditions, the data collection and evaluation in the sense of traceability of their research activities (Kaiser, 2014).

Narrative interviews

Neither a questionnaire nor a guide is to be used in the narrative interview. Also, the term "interview" is often felt to be too narrow for this procedure. Rather, it is a research situation in which the researcher merely gives the impulse for a story or an event to be told and explained without intervening in the narrative by asking further questions or directing the conversation. It is only at the end of the process, when it is a matter of clarifying ambiguities or gaps, that action by the researcher is, by definition, advised and sometimes necessary in practice. However, the processing of such collected information is complex and the interpretation often challenging (Atteslander, 2010).

Stage 4: Interactive involvement

Starting with level 4, one can speak of participation in the actual sense as stakeholders change from the position of the respondent to that of the contributor and methods move from a mere questioning on to an interactive, joint approach.

M
E
T
H
O
D
S

Expert panels

Workshops

Focus groups/Round tables

SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis is a well-known and established tool not only business, but also in research that is helpful when engaging participants of workshops (Wollny & Paul, 2015). In a SWOT analysis, the strengths and weaknesses, often referred to as internal factors, of an object of investigation are determined in order to derive opportunities and threats, which are often considered to be external factors. The aim is to create a 4-field matrix which is used to compare these identified factors in order

to determine the current state of the object of investigation (Bruhn, 2012). The involvement of stakeholders with different backgrounds can be beneficial in obtaining different perspectives to help create a more complete picture of any situation.

Scenario technique

The scenario technique is also concerned with providing forecasts for the future. More specifically, the objective is to identify influences on an object of investigation and to determine the effects of the individual factors and their interaction. In order to achieve this ambitious goal, an optimistic scenario is first drafted in regards to the object of investigation, assuming a positive development of the influences and a positive interaction of the individual factors – a good or best-case scenario. This is contrasted with a scenario that assumes a negative development – a worst-case scenario. The purpose of this procedure is to show two extremes, and thus the entire range of possible developments as well as important factors that influence the direction towards which the object of investigation actually develops (Bruhn, 2012). In addition to the best and worst case scenarios, the most probable scenario and others based on the occurrence of specific disruptive events can be defined to create a clear picture (König & Volmer, 2008).

Group Delphi

This tool is especially suitable for the integration of relevant experts. The otherwise very complex and time-consuming procedure of the Delphi method is reduced to a format that can be realized within the timeframe of a workshop. Standardized questionnaires are answered by experts in small rotating groups to get a consensus or dissent on a certain question. The classic Delphi procedure is valued as a tool for forecasting research. However, one of the main points of criticism is that, although experts share their knowledge and expertise by filling in standardized questionnaires over several waves of questioning, the reasoning and evaluation considerations behind their answers are not recorded. By designing a group Delphi within the timeframe of a workshop lasting one to two days, the basic objective, namely to maintain consensus on an issue, remains the same. However, in the course of this kind of event, they now have the opportunity to openly discuss the results of the individual rounds and

present their reasons and considerations. In this way an open dialogue can be facilitated, leading to the identification of what the dissent consists of and the possibility of resolving it before moving on to the next round, and narrowing down what the joint consensus is (Wassermann, 2015). Crucial for a successful realization of a group Delphi is an early planning and invitation of experts and a selection of experts based on different disciplines in order not to exclude certain opinions in advance. In addition, a neutral and at the same time stimulating moderation must be provided. When preparing the questionnaires, it is important to ensure that there is a limited number of research questions to deal with. Lastly, if the results are to be published, transcripts of the workshop should be distributed to the participants after the completion of the workshop in order to enable them to add comments (Wassermann, 2015).

Victorian Calling

The Victorian Calling usually involves a symposium where previous results of surveys and other types of research are presented in order to discuss recommendations, which then are further developed by the participants. The Victorian Calling describes a method that was developed to present research results from previous surveys at transdisciplinary conferences and to discuss and further develop them together with the attendants. A particular emphasis was placed on obtaining not only mere feedback from the participants, but also targeted feedback that is incorporated into the further process of the genesis of the scientific product (Defila et al., 2015).

Stage 5: Networking

This stage represents the transition from guided and accompanied activities to stimulated, guided and independent networking among the stakeholders involved and with other groups, ideally to establish lasting and sustainable connections beneficial to defined project goals.

M
E
T
H
O
D
S

Networking events
Creation of online-forums

Stage 6: Joint creation

The last stage and thus the highest level of participation possible in MATILDE is the stage of joint creation. Here, recommendations are to be developed together with the stakeholders, which are adapted to their actual needs and life circumstances and are thus feasible in their implementation. The aim of activities carried out in this stage is to empower stakeholders to not only create those recommendations, but implement them and thus contribute not only to the predefined project goals but also to long-lasting, sustainable positive transformation processes.

M
E
T
H
O
D
S

Co-creation workshops
Open innovation workshops
Focus groups

5.5 AFTERWARDS? LIVING DOCUMENT AND STAKEHOLDER DOCUMENTATION

Stakeholder involvement is continuous process during the whole project lifetime. Ideally, networks are created during the project period which will continue to exist beyond the project term and maintain a positive process of change stimulated by the project.

Stakeholder involvement planning is not a matter which can be carried out at the beginning of a project and then ticked off as finished, but is, in the sense of agile project management a dynamic process which, above all, must be continuously adapted to changing circumstances. For this reason, this stakeholder involvement plan, which was drawn up in the initial phase of the MATILDE project, is kept alive and constantly updated by a so-called "living document". The "living document" should serve two purposes. Firstly, it should provide ongoing documentation by means of a uniform template in which work package or task which stakeholders and with which method (participation level) are currently involved. For this purpose, precise contact details of the stakeholders are also recorded. The ongoing documentation by the research partners should ultimately provide an overview of the stakeholders cooperated with in the specific country or case study region. This overview of an expanded project network per partner, which is created as a result, should also be useful for future projects.

Secondly, the "living document" is the basis for a self-reflective approach and gathers experiences, knowledge and insights on the real functioning of transdisciplinary and participatory methods as well as on challenges and successes of stakeholder involvement. Among other, it will show, which participation method works under which circumstances and if stakeholder engagement in "more rural" project areas differs from stakeholder involvement strategies in "less rural" areas. Finally, the living document will conclude with learnings of stakeholder involvement.

The stakeholder mapping and the living document should be kept continuously up-to-date. The agreed stakeholder schedule with its detailed stakeholder involvement listing should serve as a guide for the

partners, when which stakeholder with which degree of participation should be involved.

The agreed stakeholder schedule with its detailed stakeholder involvement listing should be reviewed by the work package leaders at least one month before the specific work package starts.

Table 6: Extract from the draft template of the stakeholder documentation

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
	WP	Task	Stakeholder category	Name institution/individual	Contact information	Involvement Method	Role	Planned stage of involvement	Discription	Learnings
1										
2	WP 1: management and scientific coordination									
3										
4										
5										
6										
7										
8	WP 2: operationalizing the concepts for TNCs impact assessment									
9										
10										
11										
12										
13										
14	WP 3: social impact assessment of migration									
15										
16										
17										
18										
19										
20	WP 4: economic impact assessment of migration									
21										
22										
23										
24										
25										
26	WP 5: implementation of MATILDE toolbox in ural and mountain case study regions									
27										
28										
29										
30										
31										
32	WP 6: governance, policy recommendations and solutions									
33										
34										

PLANS & SCHEDULES

6 STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT AS PLANNED PER PARTNER, WP AND TASK

In this chapter the different analyses of the templates that were returned and filled-out during the process of stakeholder identification by the partners are listed.

6.1 STAKEHOLDERS ON EUROPEAN AND GLOBAL LEVEL

From the stakeholder involvement matrices (for the template, see annex 1) returned by the partners, a synthesis of possible MATILDE stakeholders, engaged either in one of the two main foci of the project, migration and integration/inclusion or regional/rural development, at European and global levels was created, which is summarized in the following tables. As these are players with an extended circle of knowledge and influence, they could be important for all partners.

Table 7: Listings of stakeholders on European level

Level	Stakeholder name
EU-Level	Alliance in the Alps
	Commission Internationale pour la Protection des Alpes (CIPRA)
	Committee of the Regions of the EU
	Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe
	Council of European Municipalities and Regions

EU-Level

Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs Expert Group on the views of migrants in the field of migration, asylum and integration
ERASMUS Program
European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)
European Association of Journalists
European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO)
European Commission
European Council on Refugees & Exiles (ECRE)
European Data Journalism Network
European E-Mobility Association (AVERE)
European Funds for Regional Development (EFRD)
European Migrant Entrepreneurship Network (EMEN)
European Migration Network (EMN)
European Network for Rural Development (ENRD)
ENRD - Thematic Group on the Long Term Rural Vision
European Social Funds (ESF)
Network of European Metropolitan Regions and Areas (METREX)

Table 8: Listing of stakeholders on international/global level

Level	Stakeholder name
International/Global Level	CARE International
	Human Rights Watch
	International Blue Crescent Foundation (IBC)
	International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD)
	International Labour Organization (ILO)
	International Organization for Migration (IOM)
	International Red Cross
	IOM, in collaboration with Directorate of Integration and Diversity (IMDi)
	Migration Policy Institute (MPI)
	OXFAM
	Refugee Welcome International (RWI)
	Resilience in Local Governance (RESLOG)
	UNESCO
	UNFPA Bursa/Kocaeli/Eskişehir Field Associate
	UNHCR
	UNICEF
United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	
World Health Organization (WHO)	

6.2 MATRIX NETWORK MAP

By completing the stakeholder landscape matrices, a comprehensive picture of those stakeholder organizations, groups and individuals who are active in the same dimension (see chapter 5.2) in the different partner countries could be created. On the basis of these maps, further analyses and evaluations can take place, which show possibilities for stakeholder networks, that can be used for sharing information and experiences or provide a basis for future think tanks.

The processing of such an analysis is shown below as an example for the dimension "housing" in combination with the stakeholder group "asylum and refugee care". The map shows for the involved MATILDE (case study) regions

- how many stakeholders (in that case: stakeholders of asylum and refugee care) for possible involvement are identified in a first mapping in the dimension "housing".
- on which territorial level the stakeholder is active.

For identification on which territorial level the specific stakeholder of "asylum and refugee care" is active, the following labelling system is used.

If partners have identified stakeholders solely on national level, the number of stakeholders is framed with a red circle. If there are stakeholders on national and regional level identified, the red circle is filled with green color. If partners have identified stakeholders on national, regional and local level, the red circle filled with green color is marked with two asterisks. If no distinction between national, regional or local level is done, the number of stakeholders appears in a black framed circle.

Table 9: Stakeholder network map, labelling system

	Stakeholders not assigned to any level
	National stakeholders
	Regional stakeholders
	Local stakeholders

In conclusion, the matrix network map makes gaps visible to stakeholders at the different territorial levels, but also stimulates exchange and cooperation between the specific stakeholder group in the respective field of action, as it makes visible which concrete stakeholders are active in which region.¹

Figure 11: Exemplary network map based on the stakeholder landscape matrices

¹ For data protection reasons, the names of the individual stakeholders in the specific regions are not published.

6.3 AGREED SCHEDULE OF STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

The following illustration and schedule represent a synthesis of the completed stakeholder schedules by each WP-leader. The table reflects the minimum level of stakeholder involvement from the work package leader's perspective per task and stakeholder group. Because of the detailed assignment per task, a temporal connection can be established to aid in the reliable and timely planning of activities for relevant groups.

Table 10: Stakeholder involvement per WP and task as agreed on by the WP leaders

	WP2						WP3				WP4				WP5				WP6				WP7					
	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.6
Associations and clubs	1	1	/	1	3	1	2	2	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	1	1	1	/	1	4	1	1
Asylum and refugee care	1	1	/	1	3	1	2	1	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	1	1	1	/	1	4	1	1
Education and training institutions	1	1	/	1	3	1	2	2	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	6	1	3	1	/	1	4	1	1
EU-Level umbrella organizations	1	1	/	1	1	1	2	2	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	3	3	1	1	/	1	4	1	4
International umbrella organizations	1	1	/	1	1	1	2	2	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	3	3	1	1	/	1	4	1	1
Internal stakeholders	1	1	/	1	1	1	2	2	3	1	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	3	3	3	1	/	1	6	1	1
Local partner	2	1	/	1	3	1	5	5	6	4	4	/	4	4	6	3	6	6	1	6	6	3	6	6	6	4	6	6
NGOs	2	1	/	1	3	1	3	2	4	2	1	/	3	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	3	3	1	/	1	4	1	1
Non-organized/other interest groups	1	1	/	1	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	1	3	1	/	1	4	1	1
Political decision makers	1	1	/	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	2	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	3	6	6	1	1	/	1	5	1	1
Private businesses	1	1	/	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	/	1	1	/	1	4	1	1
Public administrations	1	1	/	1	1	1	5	2	5	2	2	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	3	6	6	3	1	/	1	4	1	1
Public welfare service providers	2	1	/	1	1	1	3	2	4	2	1	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	1	6	3	3	1	/	1	5	1	1
Research facilities and individual researchers	1	2	/	2	2	4	6	3	5	4	2	/	1	1	/	3	6	/	3	3	3	3	1	/	6	4	1	1
Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	1	1	/	1	1	1	2	1	3	2	1	/	2	1	/	3	6	/	1	4	1	1	1	/	1	5	1	1

Detailed Stakeholder Involvement Listing

Based on the indicated stakeholder involvement in the certain work packages and tasks (see agreed schedule of stakeholder involvement) and the MATILDE Deliverable 2.5 – Data collection guidelines, the below detailed stakeholder involvement listing was created.

Table 11: Detailed stakeholder involvement listing

WP	Task	Description	Stage	Stakeholder groups	When?
2	2.1	Mapping the spatial distribution of TCNs in MATILDE regions	Information	All stakeholders	M1-M5
			Consultation within a given framework	Local partner, NGOs, public welfare service providers	
			Interactive involvement	Research facilities and individual researchers	
2	2.2	Conceptual framework on migration in rural and mountain regions	Information	All stakeholders	M2-M6
			Consultation within a given framework	Research facilities and individual researchers	
2	2.4	Methodological framework - MATILDE matrix	Information	All stakeholders	M3-M7
			Interactive involvement	Research facilities and individual researchers	
2	2.5	Methodological framework - MATILDE toolbox and fine-tuning	Information	All stakeholders	M3-M7 & M32-34
			Consultation within a given framework	Research facilities and individual researchers	

			Open consultation	Associations and clubs, asylum and refugee care, education and training institutions, local partner, NGOs, non-organized/other interest groups	
2	2.6	Stakeholder involvement plan	Information	All stakeholders	M5-M7
			Interactive involvement	Research facilities and individual researchers	
3	3.1	Policies and governance in the social realm	Information	Non-organized/other interest groups, private businesses	M7-M11
			Consultation within a given framework	Associations and clubs, asylum and refugee care, education and training institutions, EU-Level umbrella organizations, international umbrella organizations	
			Open Consultation	NGOs, public welfare service providers	
			Interactive involvement	Political decision makers	
			Networking	Local partners, public administrations	
			Joint creation	Research facilities and individual researchers	
3	3.2	Quantitative assessment of the social impact of TCNs	Information	Asylum and refugee care, non-organized/other interest groups, political decision makers, private businesses	M7-M15
			Consultation within a given framework	Associations and clubs, education and training institutions, EU-Level umbrella organizations, international umbrella organizations, internal stakeholders	

			Open Consultation	Research facilities and individual researchers	
			Networking	Local partners	
3	3.3	Qualitative assessment of the social impact of TCNs	Open Consultation	Internal stakeholders, non-organized/other interest groups, political decision makers, private businesses, trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	M7-M15
			Interactive involvement	Associations and clubs, asylum and refugee care, education and training institutions, EU-Level umbrella organizations, international umbrella organizations, NGOs, public welfare service providers	
			Networking	Public administrations, research facilities and individual researchers	
			Joint creation	Local partners	
3	3.4	Comparative analysis and social innovation practices	Information	International umbrella organizations, non-organized/other interest groups, political decision makers, private businesses	M15-M17
			Consultation within a given framework	Associations and clubs, asylum and refugee care, education and training institutions, EU-Level umbrella organizations, NGOs, public administrations, public welfare service providers, trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	

			Interactive involvement	Local partners, research facilities and individual researchers	
4	4.1	Policies and governance in the economic realm	Information	All stakeholders	M7-M11
			Consultation within a given framework	Political decision makers, public administrations, research facilities and individual researchers	
			Interactive involvement	Local partners	
4	4.3	Qualitative assessment of the economic impact of TCNs	Information	All stakeholders	M7-M16
			Open Consultation	NGOs	
			Interactive involvement	Local partners	
4	4.4	Drafting and comparatively analysing countries reports	Information	All stakeholders	M16-M18
			Interactive involvement	Local partners	
5	5.1	Guidelines definition and working group for the case study implementation	Joint creation	Local partners	M14-M15
5	5.2	Data collection and data analysis	Open consultation	All stakeholders	M15-M19
5	5.3	Action-research in rural and mountain case study regions	Joint creation	All stakeholders	M19-M26
5	5.4	Analysis and synthesis of empirical data - Replicability of case studies	Joint creation	Local partners	M25-M26

6	6.1	Integration goals and political strategies in the MATILDE countries	Information	All stakeholders	M13-M14
			Open consultation	Political decision makers, public administrations, research facilities and individual researchers	
6	6.2	Policy recommendations based on stakeholders' consultations	Open consultation	EU-Level umbrella organizations, international umbrella organizations, internal stakeholders, research facilities and individual researchers	M15-M20
			Interactive involvement	Associations and clubs, asylum and refugee care, NGOs, non-organized/other interest groups, private businesses, trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	
			Joint creation	EU-Level umbrella organizations, local partner, political decision makers, public administrations, public welfare service providers	
6	6.3	Fine-tuning MATILDE toolbox for policy makers	Information	All stakeholders	M21-M30
			Open consultation	EU-Level umbrella organizations, international umbrella organizations, internal stakeholders NGOs, public welfare service providers, research facilities and individual researchers	
			Joint creation	Local partner, political decision makers, public administrations	

6	6.4	Collection of European best-practices on integration of TCNs	Information	All stakeholders	M21-M30
			Open consultation	Education and training institutions, internal stakeholders, local partner, NGOs, non-organized/other interest groups, public administrations, public welfare service providers, research facilities and individual researchers	
7	7.1	A comprehensive Dissemination and Communication Plan	Information	All stakeholders	M1-M4
			Joint creation	Local partners	
7	7.2	Matilde Visual Identity	Joint creation	Local partners	M1-M24
7	7.3	Website and Social Media	Information	All stakeholders	M1-M36
			Joint creation	Local partners, research facilities and individual researchers	
7	7.4	Dialogue with the professional and scientific community	Interactive involvement	All stakeholders	M10-M36
			Networking	Political decision makers, public welfare service providers, trade and labour unions and organized representative groups	
			Joint creation	Internal stakeholders	

7	7.5	Communication towards the General Public	Information	All stakeholders	M1-M36
			Joint creation	Local partners	
7	7.6	Exploitation of results	Information	All stakeholders	M1-M36
			Interactive Involvement	EU-Level umbrella organizations	
			Joint creation	Local partners	

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adler, R. P., & Goggin, J. (2005): What Do We Mean By “Civic Engagement”? *American Politics Research*, pp. 236–253.
- Arbeiter, F. (2016): Kreativitätstechniken. <https://dieprojektmanager.com/kreativitaetstechniken> (accessed last, 26. August 2020).
- Arnstein, S. R. (1969): A Ladder Of Citizen Participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35, pp. 216–224.
- Atteslander, P. (2010): *Methoden der empirischen Sozialforschung*. 13. Auflage. Berlin: Schmidt.
- Beck, E. (2012): *Die Vielfalt des Lebens: Wie hoch, wie komplex, warum?* Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag & Co. KGaA.
- BMBF (2020): Citizen Science – Bürger schaffen Wissen - BMBF. <https://www.bmbf.de/de/citizen-science-wissenschaft-erreicht-die-mitte-der-gesellschaft-225.html> (accessed last, 18. August 2020).
- Bona, M. (2020): Rural and mountain areas. In S. Kordel, & A. Membretti (Eds.), *Report on conceptual frameworks on migration processes and local development in rural areas. Deliverable 2.4*. https://matilde-migration.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/MATILDE_WP2_D24_Conceptual_paper_FINAL.pdf (accessed last, 28. August 2020).
- Bonney, R., Cooper, C. B., Dickinson, J., Kelling, S., Phillips, T., Rosenberg, K. V., & Shirk, J. (2009): Citizen Science: A Developing Tool for Expanding Science Knowledge and Scientific Literacy. *BioScience*, 59, pp. 977–984.
- Brandt, P., Ernst, A., Gralla, F., Luederitz, C., Lang, D. J., Newig, J., Reinert, F., Abson, D. J., & Wehrden, H. von (2013): A review of transdisciplinary research in sustainability science. *Ecological Economics*, 92, pp. 1–15.
- Brauer, K., Aigner-Walder, B., & Oberzaucher, J. (2018): Multidisziplinarität als Summe, Interdisziplinarität als Produkt und Transdisziplinarität als Potenzierung von Fächervielfalt: Eine operationale Agenda der Altersforschung am IARA. <https://www.iara.ac.at/working-paper-series-1-2018/> (accessed last, 18. August 2020).

- Brewer, G. D. (1999): The Challenges of Interdisciplinarity. *Policy Sciences*, 32, pp. 327–337.
- Bruhn, M. (2012): *Marketing: Grundlagen für Studium und Praxis*. 11. Auflage. Wiesbaden: Gabler Verlag.
- Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. J. (2012): The Quintuple Helix innovation model: global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1, 2, pp. 1-12 (DOI: 10.1186/2192-5372-1-2).
- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. J. (2009): 'Mode 3' and 'Quadruple Helix': toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 46, pp. 201-234 (DOI: 10.1504/IJTM.2009.023374).
- Cavallini, S., Soldi, R., Friedl, J., & Volpe, M. (2016): Using the Quadruple Helix Approach to Accelerate the Transfer of Research and Innovation Results to Regional Growth. <https://cor.europa.eu/en/engage/studies/Documents/quadruple-helix.pdf> (accessed last, 29. July 2020).
- Chabal, P. (2009): *Africa: The politics of suffering and smiling*. World political theories. London, New York: University of KwaZulu-Natal Press.
- Defila, R., Di Giulio, A., & Kaufmann-Hayoz, R. (2015): „Victorian Calling“ - eine Tagungsmethode für den transdisziplinären Dialog. In S. Wassermann (Ed.), *Methoden der Experten- und Stakeholdereinbindung in der sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschung* (pp. 141-164): Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- Delli Carpini, M. (2009): Civic Engagement: Definition of Civic Engagement. <https://www.apa.org/education/undergrad/civic-engagement>.
- Dransch, D., Kyba, C. C.M., Schröter, K., Yang, B., Schorlemmer, D., Barz, B., & Denzler, J. (2018): Citizen Science - gemeinsam Wissen schaffen. *System Erde*, 8, pp. 46–51.
- Ebert, F. W. (2001): Johann Peter Süßmilch - Pfarrer, Universalwissenschaftler und „Vater der deutschen Statistik“. *Daten + Analysen*, IV, pp.78-81.
- Edwards, M. (2004): *Civil Society*. 3rd edition. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Ekman, J., & Amnå, E. (2012): Political participation and civic engagement: Towards a new typology. *Human Affairs*, 22, pp. 283-300.

- Etzkowitz, H., & Leydesdorff, L. (2000): The dynamics of innovation: from National Systems and “Mode 2” to a Triple Helix of university–industry–government relations. *Research Policy*, 29, pp. 109–123.
- European Commission (2020): Integration of migrants: Public consultation. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_1364 (accessed last, 28. August 2020).
- European Commission (2016): Action Plan on the integration of third country nationals. COM (2016) 377 final. https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/what-we-do/policies/european-agenda-migration/proposal-implementation-package/docs/20160607/communication_action_plan_integration_third-country_nationals_en.pdf (accessed last, 28. August 2020).
- Finke, P. (2014): Citizen Science: Das unterschätzte Wissen der Laien. <https://www.wissenschaftsmanagement.de/buchbesprechung/citizen-science> (accessed last, 27. July 2020).
- Government of Western Australia (2015): Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines for Community Services Procurement. A Guide to undertaking Stakeholder Engagement under the Delivering Community Services in Partnership Policy. <https://www.linkwest.asn.au/documents/item/786> (accessed last, 19. August 2020).
- Hadorn, G. H., Biber-Klemm, S., Grossenbacher-Mansuy, W., Hoffmann-Riem, H., Joye, D., Pohl, C., Wiesmann, U., & Zemp, E. (2008): *Handbook of Transdisciplinary Research*. Dordrecht: Springer Science + Business Media B.V.
- Harvard Transdisciplinary Research in Energetics and Cancer Center (2012): Definitions. <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/trec/about-us/definitions/> (accessed last, 16. July 2020).
- Hasche, N., Höglund, L., & Linton, G. (2019): Quadruple helix as a network of relationships: creating value within a Swedish regional innovation system. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, pp. 1–22.
- Hearne, R., & Murphy, M. (2019): *Participatory action research: a human rights and capabilities approach, Part 1: The theory* (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3250320).

- Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., & Vogel, J. (2018): *Citizen science: Innovation in open science, society and policy*. ISTAR Open Access monographs. London: UCL Press.
- Hermes, G. (2006): „Nichts über uns - ohne uns!“. *Disability studies als neuer Ansatz emanzipatorischer und interdisziplinärer Forschung über Behinderung*. Neu-Ulm: AG-SPAK-Bücher.
- Hinz, U., Wegener, N., Weber, M., & Fromm, J. (2014): Digitales Bürgerschaftliches Engagement. <https://hannes-jaehnert.de/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/2014-09-18-Digitales-Buergerschaftliches-Engagement.pdf>.
- International Association for Public Participation (2017): Code of ethics. https://cdn.ymaws.com/www.iap2.org/resource/resmgr/pillars/2017_code_of_ethics-24x36_ia.pdf (accessed last, 23. August 2020).
- Jennings, M. K., & Stoker, L. (2004): Social Trust and Civic Engagement across Time and Generations. *Acta Politica*, 39, pp. 342–379.
- Kaiser, R. (2014): *Qualitative Experteninterviews: Konzeptionelle Grundlagen und praktische Durchführung*. Elemente der Politik. Wiesbaden: Springer VS.
- Kelle, U. (2007): *Die Integration qualitativer und quantitativer Methoden in der empirischen Sozialforschung: Theoretische Grundlagen und methodologische Konzepte*. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- König, E., & Volmer, G. (2008): *Handbuch systemische Organisationsberatung*. Weiterbildung und Qualifikation. Weinheim, Basel: Beltz.
- Kordel, S. (2020): Third Country Nationals. In: S. Kordel, & A. Membretti (Eds.), *Report on conceptual frameworks on migration processes and local development in rural areas. Deliverable 2.4*. https://matilde-migration.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/MATILDE_WP2_D24_Conceptual_paper_FINAL.pdf (accessed last, 28. August 2020).
- Kordel, S., & Membretti, A. (Eds.) (2020a): *Report on conceptual frameworks on migration processes and local development in rural areas. Deliverable 2.4*. https://matilde-migration.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/MATILDE_WP2_D24_Conceptual_paper_FINAL.pdf

content/uploads/2020/08/MATILDE_WP2_D24_Conceptual_paper_FINAL.pdf (accessed last, 28. August 2020).

Kordel, S., & Membretti, A. (Eds.) (2020b): *Classification of MATILDE regions. Spatial specificities and Third Country Nationals distribution in MATILDE regions. Deliverable 2.1*. https://www.academia.edu/attachments/64218273/download_file?st=MTU5ODkwOTc5MCwxOTMuMTcxLjExOS4xMzM%3D&s=swp-splash-paper-cover (accessed last, 28. August 2020).

Leifson, R. (2018): A Quadruple Helix Guide for Innovations: In For Care: Informal care and voluntary assistance: Innovation in service delivery in the North Sea Region. <https://northsearegion.eu/in-for-care/news/a-quadruple-helix-guide-for-innovations/> (accessed last, 29. July 2020).

Lepczyk, C. A., Boyle, O. D., & Vargo, T. L. V. (2020): *Handbook of citizen science in ecology and conservation*. University of California Press.

Lewin, K. (1946): Action Research and Minority Problems. *Journal of Social Issues*, 2, pp. 34-46.

MacGregor, S. P., & Carleton, T. (2012): *Sustaining innovation: Collaboration models for a complex world*. Innovation, Technology, and Knowledge Management. New York: Springer.

McTaggart, R. (2010): *Participatory action research: International contexts and consequences*. SUNY series, teacher preparation and development. Albany: State University of New York Press.

Niederberger, M. (2015): Methoden der Experteneinbindung. In S. Wassermann (Ed.), *Methoden der Experten- und Stakeholdereinbindung in der sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschung* (pp. 33-47): Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.

Pettibone, L., Bonn, A., Vohland, K., & Richter, A. (2016): Citizen science for all. A guide for citizen science practitioners. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310510151> (accessed last, 27. July 2020).

Panopoulou, E., Tambouris, E. & Konstantinos, T. (2019): SCOOP4C – Stakeholder community for once-only principle: Reducing administrative burden for citizens. D2.2 Strategic stakeholder engagement plan. https://scoop4c.eu/sites/default/files/2019-10/SCOOP4C_D22_v1.14_final_0.pdf (accessed last, 19. August 2020).

Porter, R. (1978): Gentlemen and Geology: The Emergence of a Scientific Career, 1660-1920. *The Historical Journal*, 21, pp. 809-836.

- ProClim (1997): Forum for Climate and Global Change, 1997: Research on Sustainability and Forum for Climate and Global Change, Global Change – Visions in Science Policy by Swiss Researchers. https://naturwissenschaften.ch/uuid/11743771-792b-52e6-9ab7-1f3fca220f3e?r=20200527115808_1565138487_8f642f62-1845-5ff2-9aac-d494e02ebe2d.
- Rosenbrock, R., & Hartung, S. (2012): *Handbuch Partizipation und Gesundheit*. Bern: Huber.
- Scheufele, D. A., & Shah, D. V. (2000): Personality Strength and Social Capital: The Role of Dispositional and Informational Variables in the Production of Civic Participation. *Communication Research*, 27, pp. 107–131.
- Scholz, R. W., & Tietje, O. (2002): *Embedded Case Study Methods: Integrating Quantitative And Qualitative Knowledge*.
- Skocpol, T., & Fiorina, M. P. (1999): Civic engagement in American democracy. <http://www-management.wharton.upenn.edu/guillen/Verba/Verba.Civic%20Participation.pdf> (accessed last, 24 July 2020).
- Sprondel, W. M. (1979): „Experte “und „Laie “: zur Entwicklung von Typenbegriffen in der Wissenssoziologie. In W. M. Sprondel, & R. Gratthoff (Eds.), *Alfred Schütz und die Idee des Alltags in den Sozialwissenschaften*. Stuttgart: Ferdinand Enke Verlag.
- Stockemer, D. (2019): *Quantitative Methods for the Social Sciences. A Practical Introduction with Examples in SPSS and Stata*. Cham: Springer International Publishing Imprint: Springer.
- Straßburger, G., & Rieger, J. (Eds.) (2019): *Partizipation kompakt: Für Studium, Lehre und Praxis sozialer Berufe*. 2. Auflage. Weinheim: Beltz Juventa.
- Stringer, E. T. (2014): *Action research*. 4th edition. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE.
- Taiwo, R., & Opeibi, T. (2016): *The discourse of digital civic engagement: Perspectives from the developing world*. Electronics and telecommunications research. Hauppauge, New York: Nova Science Publisher's Inc.
- Töpfer, A. (2007): *Betriebswirtschaftslehre: Anwendungs- und prozessorientierte Grundlagen*. 2. Auflage. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.

- Töpfer, A. (2012): *Erfolgreich Forschen: Ein Leitfaden für Bachelor-, Master-Studierende und Doktoranden*. 3. Auflage. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg; Imprint; Springer Gabler.
- Tress, G., Tress, B., & Fry, G. (2005): Clarifying Integrative Research Concepts in Landscape Ecology. *Landscape Ecology*, 20, pp. 479–493.
- Uslaner, E. M., & Brown, M. (2005): Inequality, Trust, and Civic Engagement. *American Politics Research*, 33, 868–894.
- Värmland County Administrative Board (2019): A Quadruple Helix Guide for Innovations. In For Care: Informal care and voluntary assistance: Innovation in service delivery in the North Sea Region.
- Vetter, J. A. (2011): Introduction: lay participation in the history of scientific observation. *undefined*.
- van der Gaast, W. (2015): CARISMA – Innovation for Climate Change Mitigation. D2.2 – Stakeholder Engagement Plan.
<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e59f31f867&appId=PPGMS> (accessed last, 19. August 2020).
- von Unger, H. (2013): *Partizipative Forschung: Einführung in die Forschungspraxis*. München, Deutschland: Springer.
- Wassermann, S. (Ed.) (2015): *Methoden der Experten- und Stakeholdereinbindung in der sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschung*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- Weidinger, T. (2018): Residential mobility of refugees in rural areas of Southeastern Germany. Structural contexts as influencing factors. In S. Kordel, T. Weidinger & I. Jelen (Eds.): *Processes of Immigration in Rural Europe: The Status quo, Implications and Development Strategies* (pp. 178-202). Cambridge Scholars: Newcastle upon Tyne.
- Weidinger, T., Kordel, S., & Pohle, P. (2017): Bleiben oder Gehen? Einflussfaktoren auf die Wohnstandortmobilität anerkannter Flüchtlinge in ländlichen Räumen am Beispiel des Bayerischen Waldes. *Europa Regional*, 24, 3-4, pp. 46–61.
- Wollny, V., & Paul, H. (2015): Die SWOT-Analyse: Herausforderungen der Nutzung in den Sozialwissenschaften. In S. Wassermann (Ed.), *Methoden der Experten- und Stakeholdereinbindung*

in der sozialwissenschaftlichen Forschung (pp. 189–213): Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien
Wiesbaden.

Unpublished documents:

Dalla Torre, C., Bona, M., Bergamasco, G., Kordel, S., Weidinger, T. & Membretti, A. (2020): Deliverable 2.5
– Data collection guidelines.

MATILDE Grant Agreement No. 870831

ANNEX

ANNEX 1: TEMPLATE STAKEHOLDER LANDSCAPE MATRIX

Stakeholder category	Economy & Employment	Housing	Health	Education	Language & Culture
Associations and clubs					
Asylum and refugee care					
Education and training institutions					
Internal stakeholders					
International umbrella organizations					
EU-Level umbrella organizations					
Local partner					
NGOs					
Non-organized/other interest groups					
Political decision makers					
Private businesses					
Public administrations					
Public welfare service providers					
Research facilities and individual researchers					
Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups					

Stakeholder category	Safety & Stability	Social Connection	Rights & Citizenship	Mobility	Rural/ regional development	Dissemination & Networking
Associations and clubs						
Asylum and refugee care						
Education and training institutions						
Internal stakeholders						
International umbrella organizations						
EU-Level umbrella organizations						
Local partner						
NGOs						
Non-organized/other interest groups						
Political decision makers						
Private businesses						
Public administrations						
Public welfare service providers						
Research facilities and individual researchers						
Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups						

ANNEX 2: TEMPLATE STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT SCHEDULE

	WP1								WP2						WP3				WP4				WP5				WP6				WP7						WP8			
	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	7.1	7.2	7.3	7.4	7.5	7.6				
Associations and clubs																																								
Asylum and refugee care																																								
Education and training institutions																																								
EU-Level umbrella organizations																																								
International umbrella organizations																																								
Internal stakeholders																																								
Local partner																																								
NGOs																																								
Non-organized/other interest groups																																								
Political decision makers																																								
Private businesses																																								
Public administrations																																								
Public welfare service providers																																								
Research facilities and individual researchers																																								
Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups																																								
Joint creation	6																																							
Networking	5																																							
Interactive involvement	4																																							
Open Consultation	3																																							
Consultation within a given framework	2																																							
Information	1																																							
No involvement planned	/																																							